

PILOT GUIDELINES

VISUAL GUIDE EDITION

INTRO

Dear Stakeholders,

This guide serves both as a strategic roadmap for stakeholders and a learning tool for practitioners who wish to create participatory environments where communities become co-creators rather than beneficiaries.

The Guidelines build on Participatory Action Research (PAR) principles, combining co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and cultural responsiveness. They offer practical methods for working with vulnerable groups, safeguarding ethical standards, and promoting trust-based collaboration between communities and institutions.

WHAT IDEAL IS ABOUT

IDEAL addresses a core democratic challenge: ensuring that every voice counts, especially those too often unheard.

The project uses AI-powered multilingual tools, participatory methods, and community co-creation to reduce linguistic, cultural, and digital barriers.

Pilots

- **Belgium:** Arabic-speaking refugees
- **Austria:** Migrant/refugee women and local women
- **Greece:** Visually impaired multilingual participants

How to ensure that every voice counts, including those who are too often unheard.

PURPOSE OF THE GUIDE

Vision

This guide serves both as a strategic roadmap for stakeholders and a learning tool for practitioners who wish to create participatory environments where communities become co-creators rather than beneficiaries.

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Mission

The guide has 3 main functions:

Operational

- Shared framework for pilots
- Ethical standards
- Success indicators

Educational

- Supports facilitators
- Integrates experiential learning
- Strengthens inclusive practice

Reflective

- Encourages self-awareness
- Promotes critical thinking
- Connects theory to practice

WHO THE GUIDE IS FOR

Individual Users

- Pilot partners & facilitators
- Adult educators
- Community mediators & interpreters

Institutional Users

- Civil Society Organisations
- Local/regional authorities
- Academic institutions

Learning Ecosystem Principles

- Experience as knowledge
- Dialogue as method
- Empowerment as goal

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

IDEAL blends Participatory Action Research, adult experiential learning, and AI-assisted engagement to create a learning–action cycle where communities, facilitators, and institutions co-construct knowledge.

Participatory Action Research (PAR)

Co-design, shared inquiry, and reflection-in-action where participants act as co-researchers.

Adult Experiential Learning

Learning through doing, reflecting, adapting, and connecting lived experience to new insights.

AI-Assisted Engagement

Using translation, speech-to-text, and visualisation tools to enhance accessibility and participation.

Learning–Action Cycle with AI Touchpoints

UNDERSTANDING DEMOCRATIC VULNERABILITY

Why It Matters

Vulnerability is shaped by structural barriers, not personal traits.

Focusing on vulnerable groups strengthens democracy, improves policy quality, builds trust, and brings lived experience into decision-making.

Key Barriers

Language exclusion

Digital divides

Institutional mistrust

Cultural barriers

Accessibility gaps

Why It Matters for IDEAL

IDEAL shifts from consultation to co-ownership of democratic participation.

CONDUCTING PILOTS

The pilots test how inclusive, multilingual, and technology-assisted participation can work in real-world contexts with vulnerable groups.

Convene

Brings the right people together and motivates them to join.

Deliberate

Enables open discussion where everyone can speak and be understood.

Learn

Builds the skills needed for confident, inclusive participation

Empower

Turns participant insights into shared action and long-term involvement.

DESIGNING PILOT ACTIVITIES

The pilots are participatory learning environments that combine human interaction, digital innovation, and reflective practice to test what works in making democratic participation more inclusive.

Accessibility by Design

- Multilingual interfaces
- Screen-reader compatibility
- Plain language
- Audio/visual alternatives

Cultural Responsiveness

- Respect cultural norms
- Use storytelling
- Build psychological safety
- Adapt visuals and metaphors

AI & Digital Tools

- Real-time translation
- Speech-to-text
- Summaries
- Visualisation tools

COUNTRY APPROACHES

Belgium

Target: Arabic-speaking refugees (35–55)

Focus: civic education, multilingual access

Barriers: complex governance, linguistic inequality

Methods: hybrid workshops, translated resources

Austria

Target: migrant/refugee women + local women

Focus: empowerment, safe spaces

Barriers: isolation, discrimination, low digital skills

Methods: storytelling, scenario-based learning

Greece

Target: visually impaired multilingual participants

Focus: accessibility, AI tools

Barriers: inconsistent accessibility

Methods: peer learning, accessible platform

EVALUATION, ETHICS AND SUSTAINABILITY

Evaluation in IDEAL looks beyond outcomes to how learning, participation, and empowerment actually unfold. It checks whether inclusion, linguistic diversity, accessibility, and ethical AI are genuinely felt by participants. Managing risks is treated as an ethical responsibility, supported by a proactive, multi-layered approach.

Sustainability means carrying forward the values, relationships, and trust built during the pilots. IDEAL's legacy lies in how its inclusive methods and multilingual tools continue to be adopted and adapted across Europe.

Evaluation and Monitoring

- Mixed methods
- Participatory reflection
- Continuous adaptation

Ethical Safeguards

- GDPR compliance
- Informed consent
- Anonymisation
- AI fairness

Sustainability and Scalability

- Digital inclusion investments
- Strong local partnerships
- Policy integration
- EU community of practice

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